

The Westerner's Spiritual Quest in India in Jhabvala's *A New Dominion*

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Abstract

*The western women provide similarities in character and situation where they are stranded as vagrants moving from their native land to India and back to their homeland. They are subjected to emotional, sensitive, and sentimental problems irrespective of the differences in race, religion, culture, and creed. Women novelists concern is to probe, and analyse, into the secret recesses of their women characters and present them in flesh and blood. Jhabvala's *A New Dominion* is a continuous series of episodes, under different subheadings. Jhabvala expresses each episode in a definite form. This novel is interpreted as a variation on the theme of East-West encounter. The novel has three parts with many episodes in each part. Part one takes place in Delhi, which shows changes taking place in modern India which are harmful to the western people. The part two is located in the holy city of Banaras which exhibits the spirit of the Easterner to the westerner. The part three is in the Rajastani town of Maupur, a symbol of purity for many characters. Thus, this paper is an elaborate discussion on the spiritual quests of the westerners in India. The whites, especially women come to India with a spiritual quest to the land which offers so much, despite the clashes between tradition and modernity, be it Sanyasis, Gurus, Saints and other godly men and their system of beliefs, faith, spiritual philosophies.*

Keywords: expatriate, psychological trauma, cultural schizophrenia, spiritual, sexual moorings etc.,

The characterization of western women provides similarities in character and situation where they are stranded as vagrants moving from their native land to India and back to their homeland. The western women are subjected to emotional, sensitive, and sentimental problems irrespective of the differences in race, religion, culture, and creed. They have sexual freedom and remain strange to others to reconstruct their lives. The women writers with their sensitive perception of the human bondage tackle the situation from the perspective of the relationship between man and woman in or out of marriage which is intimate and most complex and also they handle the problems of the expatriates with their psychological trauma and cultural schizophrenia. Women novelists concern is to probe, and

analyse, into the secret recesses of their women characters and present them in flesh and blood. The quest in the novels commences with the young protagonist's decision to set out on a journey to India against all odds and ascertain for her the causes that made her to be a concubine under a King or a Nawab. The protagonist is a new woman full of confidence and with a matter of fact approach to life. She is constantly on the move, visiting a backward places, shrines, and houses and even uses computer as a process. Her quest ends as spiritual and sexual moorings.

The novel appears to be the collection of a number of episodes; each episode represents a new incident. Through this, the narrator wants to express her newly adopted technique of writing a novel. In this novel, Jhabvala presents a clear picture of India in various aspects of social, cultural, spiritual and political dimensions. Jhabvala's *A New Dominion* is a continuous series of episodes, under different subheadings. Jhabvala expresses each episode in a definite form. But, *The Unfortunates*, which is also divided into twenty seven episodes, does not have subheadings, only the first episode and the last episode have headings, and the remaining have been written at random. Perhaps, the narrator has left it to the readers to frame it according to their interpretations. Through this, it is proved that Jhabvala's way of presenting the novel has a definite purpose.

A New Dominion or *Travelers* opens with three European girls Lee, Margaret, and Evie, who try to get spiritual enlightenment under the supervision of a swami. This novel is interpreted as a variation on the theme of East-West encounter. The novel has three parts with many episodes in each part. Part one takes place in Delhi, which shows changes taking place in modern India which are harmful to the western people. The part two is located in the holy city of Banaras which exhibits the spirit of the Easterner to the westerner. The part three is in the Rajastani town of Maupur, a symbol of purity for many characters. Jhabvala describes the experiences and opinions of those Britishers and Americans Lee, Margaret and Evie in this novel, visit India in search of spiritualism and to solve their personal problems, but, their expectation come out rather badly. Jhabvala's views about India seem to be bitter against India. Haydn. M. Williams in one of the articles writes:

Throughout the novel there is much psychological analysis, often extremely probing and painful, displayed against a backdrop and death betrayals Hindu holiness, ritual, custom, passion, above all sexual passion, obsession and the frantic search for happiness which more often leads to the destruction of weaker personality. (67)

Besides these foreign characters, there are some Indian characters in this novel. Gopi is a young, dynamic, and handsome youth of a typical Indian. He is a useless, unemployed youth who is much enthusiastic to meet foreigners and come across a great friend Raymond and Lee. Through these characters, Jhabvala tries to narrate the relationship between the east and the west encounter in this novel. Rao Sahib and his wife Sunita belong to a royal family and represent a modern Indian society. Asha, Rao Sahib's widowed sister, is another important character and best example of westernized Indian woman in India. Swamiji, who resides in the Ashram, is also an important character and represents the fake Swamiji in Indian society. His character appears to be repulsive and gruesome, and behaves like an animal with all animal instincts. On the other hand, there is an old lady. Banubai, who always dedicates her life to God. She lives in Banaras, and her duty is to meet visitors and admirers those who come for help. Bul Bul and Shyam are the servants of Asha. Raymond is portrayed as a foreigner and is described with a touch of satire and humour.

The foreign women characters in Jhabvala's novels are differently portrayed in each novel. For instance, their destiny to come to India is altogether different from Lee, Margaret and Evie in *A New Dominion*. Basically, they come to India, after their marriages with Indians, find something new. Similar is the experience of Clarissa who comes to India a tourist. She feels very happy and adjusts herself to this country. But, in *A New Dominion*, Lee comes to India to find peace. Actually, she loses herself in order as she liked to put it to find herself. Not only Lee, but Margaret and Evie also come to India searching for peace as they are fed up with the mechanical life in the west.

Lee, who is the main character of this novel, travels in and out of Delhi, where she meets Gopi and Raymond. Raymond is a European who feels happy in talking with her and enjoys her company, but, Gopi an Indian feels the same but he wants something more from her. This brings out the tragedy of Lee to submit herself in order to satisfy Gopi's desire. Again, Lee meets Margaret in the mission of Miss. Charlotte, another foreign girl having the same desires. Lee says: "she was glad to be doing this for him and, at the final moment, thought to herself that perhaps this was part of the merging she had so ardently desired while looking out of the window" (48).

Lee comes to know about a Swamiji, who resides in Banaras, speaks English and does a lot for foreign disciples. She thought to visit him, along with Margaret, hoping that they might find peace and spiritual glory. During their stay in the ashram, they meet another European girl Evie. She is a personal secretary to Swamiji, who has already received the blessings of the swami. Commenting on Gurujis, Meenakshi Mukherjee writes: "The true guru is supposed to be in a state of Jivan mukta a state in which he is free from worldly bonds and desires. Though his body still performs earthly functions, his soul has already been resurrected and is in a state of union with Param Brahma" (68). Jhabvala describes the effect of Swamiji on Indian society. Swamiji in the novel mesmerizes people through his eyes and words. He behaves like an autocrat, saying that, he knows everything about the secret of life, and wants all his disciples not only spiritually, but, physically submissive to him. In the case of Lee and Margaret the same thing happens. They are influenced by Swamiji and they do everything for the sake of self-fulfillment. Lee writes to Asha that how both of them got adjusted in the ashram. Lee also tells Asha: "...I can become the new person he wants to make me and I want so much to be..." (71). In order to become a new person. Lee enters alone into a Swamiji hut at midnight, as she thinks that Swamiji might be ignoring her arrival. But, Swamiji knows everything. He is waiting for her, wastes not even a second of his time, and takes her to bed quickly by stroking her like a cat. Lee describes: "He was the only person there...drove right on into me and through me and calling me beastly names, shouting them out loud and at the same time hurting me as much as he could..." (191).

Margaret also comes to India for the quest of spiritualism and becomes a victim to Swamiji by submitting herself. She revolts against the convention ridden English society. So she refuses to act as a bridesmaid in her sister's betrothal and revolts at the last moment. She feels desperate and visits India to find peace and spiritualism. But, Swamiji knows how to attract western women. He discusses with the three western girls about the cook who has run away from the ashram. He tells Margaret that "under special decree she was appointed cook for the day" (114). She is not mentally prepared for such a task. Jhabvala writes:

Margaret kept on protesting for a while but it didn't do her any good, in the end she had to go. Swamiji continued to joke with her, but she became quite still and serious and just before she went she did a funny thing: she bent down and touched his feet.... (114)

After accepting the task of Swamiji, Margaret goes to kitchen and becomes sick. Lee observes: Margaret's condition is becoming very worse than earlier. Raymond requests her to come along with him to hospital, she does not go. Men the doctor says that she is suffering from infective hepatitis, Margaret refuses to stay at hospital: "Please don't be worried about me. I'm all right. Truly I am. Swamiji has explained it all to me so beautifully" (166).

She further adds: Doctors don't know a thing. These diseases that people get in India, they're not physical, they're purely psychic, we only get them because we try to resist India-because we shot ourselves up in our little Western egos and don't want to give ourselves. But once we learn to yield, then they just fall away. (166)

Margaret goes back to the ashram and returns after a few months, when she is nearly going to die at last; she dies in a small store room of a small hospital in Maupur. Evie obeys everything of

the sake of Swamiji. After Margaret's death, the question arises whether she is buried or cremated. Evie says: "Becoming a Hindu not like becoming a Christian. You don't have to take formal baptism or anything but freely assent to the Truth within you." (235)

Besides these three girls, there is another western character, Miss Charlotte. She runs a missionary and dedicates her life to social service for more than thirty years. Residing in India, she does a number of charitable works for the welfare of the poor, Jhabvala. Through her, Jhabvala wants to show the other side of Indian society. She is neither a seeker nor a lover, but lives in India with a definite desire to serve the sick and sufferers. Haydn. M. Williams describes: "In a novel full of searchers for spiritual peace (Asha, Lee, Margaret, Evie, perhaps even Raymond in his own way), Miss Charlotte seems the only one at peace with herself, God and India. She may have obtained the goal the seekers look for in vain" (69). Raymond, comes to India as a tourist, and remains like a tourist at the end of the novel. Because, he has no definite plans, and does not know, when he will return to his native place. He meets Gopi, an Indian and admires him as his best friend. He tells Gopi: My family has always had connections with India. One of them was in Delhi in 1835, the year when William Fraser was murdered here. He was a friend of Fraser's and wrote long letters home about the ease. We still have them. And there's a great-uncle buried somewhere near Meerut, he was killed while he was out pig-sticking..." (11).

Jhabvala's *A New Dominion* can be primarily described as the story of Lee, an English girl, who has come to India on a spiritual quest, a quest for self-realization. In fact, the west is represented by three girls Lee, Margaret and Evie. The novel deals with the dominion of India's spirituality over the forces of western materialism. Evie, Margaret and Lee are on a spiritual quest. They come to India for different reasons and meet different fates. Evie is shown in her last phase in relation to the Swami, who heads the Ashram ten miles out of Benares. She has been appointed as note-taker and chronicler of the Swami's dialogues and thoughts. Margaret has rebelled against the modern materialism of her family back home and has walked out of her own sister's wedding to find solace in India. Thus, this paper is an elaborate discussions on the spiritual quests of the westerners in India. The white, especially women come to India with a spiritual quest for the land offers so much, despite the clashes between tradition and modernity, be it Sanyasis, Gurus, Saints and other godly men and their system of beliefs, faith, spiritual philosophies. The westerners have read much of them; have seen several of them in documentary movies. Their prior knowledge in this regard has given them the impetus to move towards the Indian world to experience the exposed spirituality and thereby realize their spiritual quest.

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